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Optimization of Conditions for Mass Production of Orchid Mycorrhizal Fungi (OMF) Inoculants

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Abstract

The study determined the optimum conditions for mass production of OMF inoculants. Extracts from each of the five different locally-available materials (sorghum, SHE; rice bran, RBE; sawdust, SE; and fern chips, FE and combinations of RBE and SE) for isolation of pure culture from tissue and spores and subsequently production of "mother culture" were evaluated. Four locally available substrates (sawdust, fern chips, sorghum and rots) combined with rice bran for spawn production and interaction of temperature and substrate for fruiting bodies formation were likewise assessed.

Combination of extracts of rice bran and sawdust at 1:1 ratio and rice bran alone were found to be the most suitable media for multi-spore and tissue isolations and production of "mother culture". Sawdust and fern chips each mixed with rice bran at 1:1 ratio were found to be the best substrate for spawn production. These substrates were fully colonized with OMF mycelia four weeks after incubation at room temperature. Exposure of substrate (sawdust + rice bran) fully colonized with mycelia to cold temperature favored primordial initiation for a shorter period of time. Larger and heavier basidiocarps were obtained from these substrates.

Keywords: basidiocarp, fruiting bodies, orchid mycorrhizal fungi

Abbreviations: FCEA- fern chips extract agar; MEA- malt extract agar; OMF- orchid mycorrhizal fungi; PDA- potato dextrose agar; RBEA- rice bran extract agar; RBSEA- rice bran and sawdust extract agar; REA- root extract agar; SEA- sawdust extract agar and SHEA- sorghum extract agar.

INTRODUCTION

The orchid mycorrhizal fungi play a major role in the survival of the orchids species. Mycorrhizal fungi provide mineral nutrition to both the germinating seedlings and adult orchids in cases when the roots are inefficient for absorption (Brown, *et al.*, 1997). Fungi are also implicated in the process of orchid seed germination. According to Peterson, *et al.* (1996), germinating orchid seeds depend on the establishment of a relationship with soil fungi to provide nutrients. The degradation and assimilation of starch reserves by the orchids during fungal invasion until digestion of the fungi contribute to the enhancement of orchid growth (Uetake, *et al.*, 1992). During the course of fungal interaction with the orchids, the morphological changes of the symbionts are mediated by the alterations of the cytoskeleton, specifically the actin filaments (Uetake and Peterson, 1997) and the microtubules (Uetake, *et al.*, 1997). These cytoskeletal elements enable the orchid cells to eliminate its fungal

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invaders through the deposition of cell wall around the cells. These events show that once the seedlings can grow independently, the mycelial hyphae within the cells will cease to function.

Studies on the role of OMF on seed germination and early growth of the orchids started in 18th century (Arditti, 1989). However the function of mycorrhizal association in adult green orchids has received no attention at all. Research on OMF in the country was initiated only in 1995 by the Vesicular Arbuscular Mycorrhiza (VAM) group at BIOTECH. It was observed that the growth of tissue-cultured orchids (waling-waling) contaminated with fungi grew more vigorous and healthier compared with uncontaminated seedlings. Studies also investigated the significant long-term effect of orchid mycorrhizal fungi in increasing growth rate of the orchid and their ability to deter root pathogen infection. Mycorrhizal orchids produced flowers much earlier compared to non-mycorrhizal ones (Brown, et al. 1997). However, the availability of OMF inoculants was hampered due to lack of knowledge on mass production of the fungal symbionts.

This study was therefore conducted at the National Institute Molecular Biology and Biotechnology (BIOTECH), University of the Philippines Los Baños from June 2004 to March 2006 to optimize the conditions for mass production of orchid mycorrhizal fungi inoculants for commercial purposes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Selection of Locally Available Culture Medium for “Mother Culture” Cultivation

Sources, Isolation and Maintenance of Isolates

For tissue culture, two to three mm tissues obtained from the top head portion of the basidiocarp were surface sterilized with 10% chlorox for ten minutes. These were rinsed three times with sterilized distilled water, blotted dry and were placed on the surface of the prepared media in petri dishes. These were incubated at room temperature until mycelial growths were observed.

For multi spore isolation, spore suspensions with a concentration of 10-20 spores / ml was prepared and was allowed to germinate at low temperature. One ml of pre-germinated spores were either spread evenly on the surface of the petri dish of prepared agar media or in flask with liquid media

Two stock culture isolates from BIOTECH coded as MBF3 and MBF5 were revived using malt extract agar (MEA) and potato dextrose agar (PDA) media. Two other isolates coded as MBF7 and MBF9 were isolated from newly collected basidiocarp of OMF.

Media Preparation

Two hundred grams from each of the identified locally-available substrates: acacia roots, fern chips, sawdust, rice bran, potato and dried sorghum seeds were used for the preparation of 1L media. These were blended at 5-10 min, then the solution was filtered using number 2-whatmann filter paper in an Erlenmeyer flasks. For solid media preparation, the filtrate was mixed each with 18 g of agar-agar. The different formulations were mixed gently with the use of stirring rod to completely dissolve the powder. The media were cooked for 10 min or until sticky solution was observed. Thereafter the required volume of media was dispensed into an Erlenmeyer flask and was sterilized at 15 psi for 15 to 20 min.

Plating and Inoculation

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About 10 µl of lactic acid was added into a sterile 250 ml of media before pouring into a sterilized petri plates under the laminar flow hood. The media were allowed to solidify for 20-30 min before inoculation.

A 7 mm in diameter sterilized cork borer was used for obtaining uniform mycelial growth of 7-day old OMF isolates previously grown on MEA plates. These were placed at the center of the plates with different agar media or in liquid broth in flasks. The plates were incubated at room temperature for 9 days while the flasks were incubated at room temperature for 7 days in rotary shaker.

Data Gathered

Mycelial diameter was measured to determine the effect of the different media on the mycelial growth. Descriptive growth quality was observed in each of the different media. Mycelial thickness, color and number of days to colonize the surface of the plates were likewise recorded.

Experimental Design

Experiment for solid media evaluation was laid out in factorial design in a Completely Randomized Design (CRD) with 3 replications. Six media preparation from locally available substrates and two standard media were designated as Factor A and four isolates were designated as Factor B. A total of 96 plates were used in the experiment with a factorial combination of 8 x 4 x 3 which was replicated 3 times. For liquid broth only one isolate was used and the experiment was laid-out in completely randomized design (CRD).

Selection of Locally Available Substrate for Spawn Production and Fruiting Bodies Formation

“Mother Culture” Preparation

Four OMF isolates coded as MBF3, MBF5, MBF7 and MBF9 were used in the study. Starter culture (G1 master culture) production of these isolates were done using sorghum as substrate. Sorghum seeds were boiled for 30 min; air-dried for 1 hour and were transferred in a sterilized catsup bottle. The bottle containing 300 g of boiled sorghum was tightly closed with rubber stopper and sterilized in the autoclave at 15 psi for 15-20 min. These were inoculated with 3 mm agar block with OMF growth using cork borer. The inoculated bottles were incubated for 7 days at ambient conditions.

Substrate Preparation

The different substrate combinations used in this study were based on the recommendation of previously conducted experiment in the mass production of mycelia and spawn. These were rice bran + sorghum; rice bran + chopped acacia roots; rice bran + sawdust and rice bran + fern chips at 1:1 ratio.

Rice bran was the base substrate in all the treatments. Rice bran was mixed with each of equal volume of boiled sorghum, chopped partially-decomposed acacia roots; sawdust; and fern chips. Each mixture was added with 1% lime solution. The combined substrates were tightly closed with plastic sheets and allowed to decompose. Two weeks thereafter, the partially-decomposed substrates were placed in an autoclavable plastic bag measuring 4 x 3.5 inches. The moisture content was adjusted using the fist method (Gabriel, 2004, Reyes, *et al.*, 2004). The substrates were sterilized three times at 15 psi for 1 hour.

Bag Inoculation

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Each bag was inoculated with one teaspoon of sorghum colonized with OMF. The bags were tightly closed with 5 x 2 mm diameter PVC pipes plugged with sterilized cotton. Inoculated bags with G1 master sorghum seeds were incubated at room temperature for mycelial colonization.

Experimental Design

Two factorial designs in a Complete Randomized Design were used in the study. The three isolates were the Factor A. The different substrates were assigned as Factor B. Factor combinations were 4 x 4 x 3 replicated three times with a total of 48 experimental units.

Data and Parameters Used

Percentage mycelial colonization of the different substrates was evaluated at weekly interval for 4 weeks. Quantitative description was done using class index for colonization developed by Luis *et al.*, 1998 (Table 4). The color of the inoculated bags was examined since this is an indicator of growth as cited by Flegg (2000). Silverio and Vilella (1982) also reported that the substrate is fully colonized when the bags becomes impregnated with white to light yellow of mycelial growth of the spawn. Mycelial biomass such as fresh and dry weight was also gathered to determine efficacy of the substrates for spawn production.

Interaction Effect of Temperature and Combined Mixtures of Substrate for Fruiting Bodies Formation

After the mycelium has fully colonized the substrate, the conditions that encouraged fruiting body formation were determined. In general, the key to fruiting formation relies on altering the surrounding environment. In this study the effect of temperature and substrates were evaluated. Factorial experiment was laid-out in a completely randomized design. Four different isolates (MBF3, MBF5, MBF7 and MBF9) were designated as Factor C. Data gathering like number of primordial produced, days to produce primordia and size and weight of basidiocarp were recorded. Four combination of substrates were prepared and the following was designated as Factor A. T1- Rice bran + sorghum, T2- Rice bran + chopped acacia roots, T3- Ribe bran + saw dust and T4- Rice bran + fern chips. The substrates were first allowed to fully colonize by OMF at room temperature for homogenous experimental units prior to exposure to different temperature. These factors are E1-Room temperature, E2- 21°C (air conditioned room) and T3- outdoor temperature. A total of 96 bags containing mycelial spawn was used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Selection of Locally Available Culture Medium for “Mother Culture” Cultivation

Morphological Characteristics of Mycelial Growth

Combination of rice bran and sawdust extract (RBSEA) was found to be the most effective culture medium among the 8 culture media evaluated (Table1). Mycelial growth of the four isolates in RBSEA was significantly higher than in other media including potato dextrose agar (PDA) and malt extract agar (MEA) which served as the standard media. This was observed during the 6 and 9 DAI (Fig 1).

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Table 1. Mycelial growth measurements (diameter in cm) of four species of orchid mycorrhizal fungi (OMF) as affected by different culture media.

Culture Media*	MBF3			MBF5			MBF7			MBF9		
	3	6	9	3	6	9	3	6	9	3	6	9
PDA	2.90 cd	6.63 b	8.10 b	2.13 b	8.13 b	8.36 c	2.00 c	6.16 c	6.43 cd	4.30 b	6.96 a	7.13 b
MEA	2.83 c	6.13 c	8.13 b	2.13 b	8.03 b	8.23 b	2.00 c	6.06 c	6.26 d	4.26 bc	6.30 b	7.30 b
SHEA	3.16 b	6.06 c	8.03 b	2.60 a	7.20 c	7.40 d	2.50 b	5.23 d	5.96 d	4.06 cd	6.23 b	6.30 c
RBEA	3.86 a	4.26 d	6.53 d	2.00 bc	6.20 d	6.43 e	1.80 d	3.00 e	3.73 e	3.13 e	6.13 b	6.36 c
REA	3.10 bc	6.26 bc	8.03 b	2.80 a	8.10 b	8.36 bc	2.96 a	6.13 c	6.86 bc	4.16 bcd	6.13 b	7.13 b
SEA	2.90 d	6.23 bc	7.36 c	1.20 d	8.50 a	8.63 b	1.20 f	6.96 b	7.23 b	4.20 bc	6.10 b	7.10 b
FCEA	3.13 b	6.23 bc	8.10 b	1.60 cd	8.03 b	8.10 c	1.60 e	6.36 c	6.86 bc	3.96 d	5.30 c	7.23 b
RBSEA	3.13 b	7.23 a	8.56 a	1.70 bc	8.70 a	8.96 a	1.70 de	8.70 a	9.00 a	5.93 a	6.36 a	7.96 a
Level of significance	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**
Coefficient of variation (cv)	3.81	2.11	2.11	5.14	2.71	3.69	4.86	2.33	2.88	2.70	1.86	4.69

** = Highly significant

Means in a column having the same letter are not significantly different at 5% level (DMRT).

- * PDA- Potato Dextrose Agar
- MEA- Malt Extract Agar
- SHEA- Sorghum Extract Agar
- RBEA- Rice Bran Extract Agar
- REA- Root Extract Agar (acacia)
- SEA- Sawdust Extract Agar
- FCEA- Fern Chips Extract Agar
- RBSEA- Rice Bran and Sawdust Extract Agar

Fig. 1. The effect of the different locally available culture media on the mycelial growth of four orchid mycorrhizal fungi (OMF) isolates 9 days after incubation at room temperature. REA- root extract agar, SEA- saw dust extract, agar, FCEA- fern chips extract agar, RBSEA- rice bran and saw dust extract agar, PDA- potato dextrose agar, MEA- malt extract agar.

Mycelial growth of the four isolates in rice bran extract agar (RBEA) and sawdust extract agar (SEA) when used singly was significantly lower compared to their growth in combined rice bran and saw dust extract agar

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(RBSEA). The growth rate as exhibited by the diameter of the mycelial growth was found to be higher in RBSEA than in other media preparation (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Growth rate of four orchid mycorrhizal fungi (A. MBF3, B. MBF5) isolates as affected by different media. REA- root extract agar, SEA- saw dust extract agar, FCEA- fern chips extract agar, RBSEA- rice bran and saw dust extract agar, PDA- potato dextrose agar, MEA- malt extract agar.

The above results indicated that rice bran and saw dust have components that enhanced the growth of the OMF mycelia. Brown, Boado and Santillan (2005) recommended the use of combination of either rice bran and sawdust or rice bran and fern chips as a substrate for spawn production. Rice bran alone contained high concentration of thiamine as well as nitrogen as carbon source. These components were essential nutrients for mycelial growth and reproduction of fungi. It was also reported by Stamets (1993), Stamets (2000) and Yamanake, (1997) that sawdust or wood chips combined with rice bran have high nitrogen-rich components.

Mycelial Biomass

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The four OMF consistently had the highest fresh and dry weight in RBSEA medium. MBF 7 have the highest fresh weight (353.0 g) followed by MBF3 (347.70 g) and MBF 9 (341.0 g). The same trend was also observed for the dry weight which ranged from 108-118.30 grams (Figure 3).

Fig. 3. Mycelial biomass production of four orchid mycorrhizal fungi (OMF) isolates (A. MBF3, B. MBF5, C. MBF7, D. MBF9) in different culture media 9 days after inoculation. REA- root extract agar, SEA- saw dust extract agar, FCEA- fern chips extract agar, RBSEA- rice bran and saw dust extract agar, PDA- potato dextrose agar, MEA- malt extract agar, WEA- wheat extract agar.

Fresh weight and diameter of mycelial growth in different liquid culture

Combination of rice bran and sawdust extracts and rice bran extract were found to be the most suitable liquid media for spore culture. This was exhibited by the fresh weight of germinated growth of spore five days after incubation at room temperature in rotary shaker. The diameter of mycelial growth of OMF grown in these two media was significantly larger compared to their growth in other media.

Physical appearance of culture media and morphological characteristics of isolates

Potato dextrose agar (PDA) and MEA appeared light yellow and brown respectively. SHEA and SEA media were dark brown in color while FCEA was black in color. RBEA looked dirty white while mixtures of RBSEA appeared chocolate brown color.

All the isolates grew profusely and fully colonized RBSEA from 5-7 days only. They appeared dirty white and very thick aerial mycelium formed on these two media. On the other hand, the isolates were observed thin and colored white on PDA, MEA, SHEA, SEA and FCEA. Number of days to fully-colonized these media ranged from 9-12 days after inoculation.

Utilization of Locally Available Substrate for the Production of Spawn and Fruiting Bodies Formation

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Weekly Colonization

The four orchid mycorrhizal fungi (OMF) isolates grew on the four substrates tested such as rice bran + sorghum, rice bran + acacia roots, rice bran + saw dust and rice bran + fern chips (Fig. 4). In week 1, it was observed that mycelial colonization ranged from 3.0 to 9.33 %. From the four substrates tested, mixture of rice bran and fern chips had the highest percentage mycelial colonization of the 4 OMF isolates which ranged from 8.67 to 9.33 %.

Fig. 4. Percent mycelial colonization of four orchid mycorrhizal fungi (OMF) isolates (A. MBF3, B. MBF5, C. MBF7, D. MBF9) as affected by different substrate combinations.

Mycelial colonization drastically increased (30-34%) at the second week of incubation, however it the trend was the same (Fig. 4). Rice bran and fern chips still had the highest percentage mycelial colonization of three isolates MBF3, MBF5 and MBF7) which ranged from 27-34 %. One isolate MBF7, however preferred rice bran + sawdust. This was followed by substrate combination of rice bran and saw dust with a ranged of 26-34 % for the three isolates. Rice bran + sorghum seeds and rice bran + chopped acacia roots exhibited the lowest mycelial colonization ranging only from 14.33 to 21.67 % and 18.33 to 23.33, respectively. During the third week of incubation, the different substrates were colonized with almost 73 %. MBF9 isolates responded well with 73 % colonization in a substrate combination of rice bran and fern chips. The three remaining isolates responded differently. Combination of rice bran and saw dust was found to be the most suitable as substrate for the three OMF isolates; MBF3, MBF5 and MBF7 with mycelial percent growth of 77, 71.6 and 70.6, respectively.

In the fourth week of incubation, almost all the combined substrates were fully colonized by OMF mycelia. Combination of rice bran and sawdust was equally effective to that of fern chips at this period which was statistically different for the first three weeks. The bags with the substrates were more compacted and appeared to have more mycelium compared to bags with substrate mixture of rice bran + sorghum and rice bran + chopped acacia roots. The four OMF isolates recorded mycelial colonization which ranged from 95 to 100% for

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rice bran + saw dust followed by rice bran + fern chips (91-95%), rice bran + chopped acacia roots (43.33-74.67) and rice bran + sorghum (70.00-73.33%).

The above results indicated that either fern chips or saw dusts mixed with rice bran at 1:1 ratio are suitable and the best substrates for spawn production. These mixtures had components that enhanced fungal growth. According to Aristotle, (2005), rice bran have higher moisture content. Moreover, it was investigated also by Silverio, et al. (1981) that rice bran contained high concentration of thiamine as well as nitrogen as carbon source. On the other hand, Buzhardt, (2002) proved that coco sawdust contained high amount of cellulose. Carbon sources such as nitrogen are important requirement for the secretion of cellulolytic enzyme which are involved in the hydrolysis of cellulose and eventually converted into an available form as a carbon source in the form of glucose (Silverio, et al. 1981). Rice bran was used because this was previously proven by Santillan et al. (2004) to be the best medium and was even better if mixed with appropriate combination of substrate for OMF spawn production. Rice bran contained approximately 92.0% of protein which had similar properties in comparison with egg according to Wang (1999). It also contains cycloartenol ferulic acid ester a component of gamma-oryzanol which is a phytosterol (Hiraga *et al.* 1993 and myo-inositol derivatives which was considered as growth factor for mushroom (Ogawa, 1999).

Nitrogen, biotin and thiamine are also important to promote spawn growth (Alexopoulos, 1962). Nitrogen is especially important in the release of hydrolytic enzymes (cellulolytic, lipolytic and proteolytic enzymes) involved in the hydrolysis of complex organic materials into simple, soluble organic compounds (Silverio, et al. 1981). Doubleday, (2003) also studied that sawdust have higher water retention and aeration. Hopkins, (1998) also added that glucose is the primary component of cellulose in plant cell walls, therefore allowing the growth of mycelia when inoculated in substrates composed of plant matter. Other components of the substrate like sorghum, sawdust, fern chips and root extracts might have complex system of several simple phenolic compounds, instead of glucose constituents (Hopkins, 1998).

Interaction Effect of Temperature and Combined Mixtures of Substrate for Fruiting Bodies Formation

Aside from the effect of the temperature, the interaction effect of substrate that was the combination of rice bran with other sources like sorghum, acacia roots, saw dust and fern chips was evaluated.

Number of Primordia

Temperature significantly affects the number of primordium produced by MBF3 and MBF5 grown in mixture of rice bran + sawdust. They produced more primordium when exposed to cold temperature than in room and outdoor temperature. Primordial initiation was induced by exposure to low temperature. Other mushroom like oyster has been found to fruit after exposing the bags fully colonized with mycelia (Kwon, 2004). Performing a cold-shock or lowering the temperature of growing room to 15-18°C depending on species or strains of oyster mushroom is now being practiced (Choi, 2004).

Flegg (2004) found out that the mycelial growth of the reishi medicinal mushroom (*Ganoderma lucidum*) increased with the increase of the wheat bran or rice bran rate added to the basal saw dust medium up to 20% supplementation but leveled off thereafter. He found that higher number of primordia produced when rice bran was used in fruiting bodies production.

All the four isolates used in the study responded similarly and were significantly affected by different temperature as evidenced by the measurement of basidiocarp length and weight.

Basidiocarp length was significantly affected by different conditions. Likewise, the interaction of the different combination of substrates and exposure to different temperature was also significant. For MBF3, it was observed that exposures to cold temperature, resulted basidiocarp length which ranged from 9.33 to 12.20 cm. When this was exposed to room and outdoor temperature there was only a slight increased in basidiocarp length and had an average length of 4.10 to 6.40 cm only. A significant difference was also observed in different combinations of substrate. Combination of rice bran + sawdust recorded the highest measurement of basidiocarp length of 12.20 cm. Lower basidiocarp length was observed from the remaining mixtures of substrates which ranged only from 9.33 to 10.93 cm. (Fig. 5A). Significant interaction of the temperature and the substrates used was observed in MBF5 isolate. It exhibited the highest length measurement with a mean value of 12.63 cm when this was exposed to cold temperature and grown in rice bran + sawdust. No significant interaction of temperature when the substrates when exposed to either indoor or outdoor temperature. This means that MBF5 isolate would performed well at cold temperature using rice bran + sawdust as a substrate (Fig. 5B).

Fig. 5. Basidiocarp formation (length) of orchid mycorrhizal fungi (OMF) (A) MBF3 (B) MBF5 as affected on the basidiocarp length as affected by exposure to different temperatures and combination of substrates.

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The same effect was observed for MBF3 and MBF7 isolates in terms of basidiocarp length. Significant interactions were observed when the different substrates with these 2 isolates were exposed to different temperatures. Combinations of substrate, rice bran and sawdust produced the largest basidiocarp with an average length of 13.53 cm under cold temperature (Fig. 6A). Significant interaction of temperature and the substrates used were also observed in MBF9 isolate. Combination of rice bran + sawdust exposed to cold temperature had the highest basidiocarp length (12.77 cm, Fig. 6B). Although, significant interaction of substrate to the indoor and outdoor temperature, lower values were observed which ranged only from 5.10 to 6.87 cm. This means that even if it was significant, the degree of magnitude of increased was too small compared to the double value observed at cold temperature using rice bran + saw dust as a substrates.

The results of the study proved that at lower temperature and using appropriate substrate would lessen time to produce fruiting bodies. The results of the study jived with the study conducted by Lee (2003). He found out that at lower temperature development of fruiting bodies of *Ganoderma* produced bigger size hence, higher yield was observed. In his study, he used a temperature ranged from 25 °C to 32 °C. Our study tried to expose the inoculated bags even at lower temperature from 12 °C to 16°C to determine its response from this condition. Positive results were obtained as evidenced by producing bigger size of basidiocarp at shorter period of time.

Fig. 6. Basidiocarp formation (length) of orchid mycorrhizal fungi (OMF) (A) MBF7 (B) MBF9 as affected on the basidiocarp length as affected by exposure to different temperatures and combination of substrates.

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Dry Weight of Basidiocarp

The four isolates responded similarly but were significantly affected by different temperatures and combined mixtures of substrates. In low temperature, MBF5 recorded the highest dry weight (82.90 g), MBF3 (81.67 g), MBF9 (74.67 g) and MBF7 (74.0 g) using combined mixtures of rice bran and sawdust. Values observed at indoor as well as on outdoor condition produced lower weight, which ranged from 31.67 g to 38.10 g. This results indicated that exposure to cold temperature enhanced fruiting development in substrate which was a combined mixtures of rice bran + sawdust. Significant interaction were also observed from the remaining combined mixtures of substrates like rice bran + sorghum, rice bran + acacia roots and rice bran + fern chips, although the degree of increase was small.

Data on dry yield proved that better yield produced significantly higher when right temperature and appropriate mixtures of substrates were used. Aside from the right temperature, some other factors like moisture content might affect spawning according to Beetz and Kustudia (2004) and fruiting body formation. As in the case of the treatment under cold temperature the bags definitely had higher moisture content. At this condition, faster fruiting development would be enhanced. The ideal moisture content for a healthy growth of almost all basidiomycetes is 60-70% (Davis and Aegeter, 2000). They also added that mycelia colonization is better at higher temperature and shifted to a lower temperature when fruiting starts to develop. Flegg (2000) also cited that spawn running is generally around 13 to 14 days after bag inoculation for oyster mushroom. Spawn run observed in this study was shorten because it was observed that 100% mycelial colonization took one week only after bag inoculation and started to develop fruiting primordium.

Other factors that affect fruiting bodies formation include relative humidity, lighting and CO₂ concentration but these were not considered in this study. Davis and Aegeter (2000) also reported that the degree of compactness would also a factor for better yield. More compact substrates enhance better colonization, faster fruiting development, bigger size and finally higher yield.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Extract from each of the five different locally-available substrates (sorghum, SHE; rice bran, RBE; acacia roots, RE; sawdust, SE and fern chips, FE) and combination of extracts from rice bran and sawdust (RBSE) were evaluated as main component of culture media for OMF isolation and “mother culture” cultivation. Extracts from potato (P) and Malt Extract Agar (MEA) was included in the evaluation as standard media. For solidified agar media preparation 18g of agar (A) was added to each extracts. For the standard medium (PD) 18g of dextrose was added.

Two out of eight culture media preparations which were RBE and RBSE were found effective in culturing the four isolates of OMF. For tissue culturing, RBSEA consistently supported the highest increment of mycelial growth with thick aerial growth in a short period of time. Although the radial growth of the 4 isolates in RBEA was found to be slow their aerial growth was thicker and better than in other media preparation including the standard media used. For multi spores isolation, RBSE and RB were found to be the most suitable liquid media used. Growths of spore were larger in diameter compared to the growth in other media.

For spawn production, four substrates in combination with rice bran at 1:1 ratio (rice bran + sorghum, acacia roots, saw dust and fern chips) were evaluated for the four OMF. From the four substrates tested combination of rice bran and fern chips recorded the highest percentage mycelial colonization in all of the OMF isolates during the first week of observation.

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In the fourth week of incubation however, combination of rice bran and sawdust was equally effective to that of fern chips wherein all the substrates were fully-colonized with mycelia. For fruiting body formation, more primordium was produced in substrate (rice bran + saw dust) fully colonized with mycelia when exposed to cold temperature. Likewise basidiocarp length and weight obtained from substrates exposed to cold-shock were higher than in substrates that were exposed to room and outside temperature.

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